

CULTiVATE

Research protocol for the analysis of food governance landscapes in HUB cities

WP 4, T 4.1

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1. Introduction

This document provides detailed guidelines to conduct the analysis of the food governance landscape of the three CULTIVATE Hub locations. Taking the cities of Barcelona, Milano and Utrecht as case studies, the aim is to identify different governance models and their impacts on Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs), with particular attention to the influence of policies at different administrative levels: local, regional, national and European. The analysis will be centered around three food sharing arenas because of their significant impact and relevance in the Hub locations: food waste and redistribution (particularly important in Milano), social and solidarity economy (prominent in Barcelona), and urban agriculture (most consolidated in Utrecht). The three locations will analyse the three arenas to allow comparison among them, but with different priority due to time limitations.

- Barcelona: primary focus SSE (social and solidarity economy), secondary focus FWR (Food waste and redistribution), tertiary focus UA (urban agriculture).
- Milano: primary focus FWR, secondary focus UA, tertiary focus SSE
- Utrecht: primary focus UA, secondary focus FWR, tertiary focus SSE

This food governance landscape analysis is part of the collation phase of the Work Package 4 (WP4) of the CULTIVATE project, more specifically Task 4.1. It is informed by a scope review and related policy brief on urban and peri-urban (UPU) food governance which was completed in June 2023 as part of the same task. The analysis focuses on food governance landscapes of the three locations in relation to three types of urban food sharing, and includes a comparative phase after the three cities have been studied. In order to explore these governance landscapes three research questions are defined (and further subquestions identified to ground the analysis (see Table 2)). The methodology will include a combination of desk-based research analysis and semi-structured interviews with key informants in order to gather relevant data to address the research questions. The interviews will help uncover further data and documents that will be added to the qualitative analysis and therefore, will be part of an interactive research process. Furthermore, this task is embedded in CULTIVATE and other project activities will take place in parallel which might contribute to refine the analysis and provide additional insights and data, such as WP2 mapping activities and WP3 mobile research labs. Below there is a summary of research questions and key methodological aspects:

- RQ1: How are regulatory regimes shaping food sharing landscapes, and what is their impact on FSIs?
The analysis of regulatory regimes will mostly focus on analysing policy, regulatory and strategic documents on the one hand, and on the other on mapping key actors, their main governance activities and their relations.
RQ1 will be mostly addressed by the desk-based analysis of key documents and complemented with primary data consisting of semi structured interviews to key stakeholders.

- RQ2: What are the main place-based enablers for and barriers to sustainable food sharing in the three Hub locations?

This analysis is the core of the exercise since it will constitute a key tool to inform task 4.2 (local scenarios and design of transition pathways workshop) but also support efforts at the local level to improve urban food sharing and therefore contribute to food security and food justice in the selected cities.

RQ2 will be addressed through qualitative analysis of key documents and primary data consisting of semi structured interviews to key stakeholders. We will also coordinate with WP3 to include insights from 12 FSIs recruited during Task 3.1.

- RQ3: What is the influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context in shaping FSIs in the Hub locations?

Addressing this research question requires identifying the main cultural and socio-ecological aspects that have contributed to shaping the local food sharing landscape, including how multilevel governance dynamics play a role in shaping FSIs.

RQ3 will be mostly addressed by the desk-based analysis of key documents and complemented with primary data consisting of semi structured interviews to key stakeholders

Once the present research is completed, the findings will be discussed among partners from Spoke locations to explore commonalities and divergences in terms of enablers and challenges of food sharing governance, adding further nuance and validation to the comparative analysis. The main enablers and challenges identified for the governance of FSIs will also contribute to co-designing six workshops that will be held as part of the activation phase of the WP4, Task 4.2. In these, we will conduct a participatory backcasting process to identify feasible paths to desirable future UPU food sharing scenarios. Learnings will also be included in the Menu for Good Governance to guide action locally. The results from this research will be shared and published in academic outlets.

This investigation aims to have an impact beyond pre-defined CULTIVATE activities. More specifically, this analysis aims to inform policy making processes on the ground, and to provide business and societal actors with tools to better understand and navigate food sharing governance in the different cities involved (and beyond). Our ultimate goal is to support the development of progressive food sharing policies and to strengthen local food sharing economies.

The analysis runs from June 2023 to March 2024 (M6 to M15 of the CULTIVATE project) and it involves the following people and levels of dedication:

Table 1: Partners and people involved in the comparative analysis

Hub location	Partner	PM (for T4.1)	Person	Position
Barcelona	UB	16	Ana Moragues Faus	Team leader
			Amaranta Herrero Cabrejas	Postdoc researcher
			Sergio Ruiz Cayuela	Postdoc researcher
	PEMB	4	Gunilla Meurling	Team leader
Milano	MIL	8	Matteo Matteini	Project manager
Utrecht	WU	4	Kim Medema	Researcher

			Lucie Sovová	Team co-lead
			Jessica Duncan	Team co-lead
	UTR	1	Imara Antonius	Local CULTIVATE project leader
			Freek Liebrand	Senior Policy Advisor Healthy Living Environment
-	ULUND	1,5	Vera Sadovska	Postdoc researcher
			Yuliya Voytenko Palgan	Team co-lead
-	TCD	1	Anna Davies	Team leader

Table 2: Summary of research questions and specific elements to include in the analysis.

Research question	Questions to guide analysis	Further guidance	Examples	Data sources
<p>How are regulatory regimes shaping food sharing landscapes, and what is their impact on FSIs?</p> <p><i>Caveat: regulatory regimes are a linked set of policies, institutions, discourses and powers that condition the relationship between societal interests, the state, and economic actors. We don't have the time or tools to analyse these in depth and their impact on FSIs, so we focus on the policy and regulatory frameworks and a light stakeholder analysis to characterise some of these regimes.</i></p>	<p>What are the main policies, regulations and plans regarding FWR/UA/SSE in the city? Are there regional, national and/or European policies shaping urban FWR/UA/SSE in the city?</p> <p><i>Max. 2000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe the policies and regulations that have an impact on the city FSIs dealing with FWR/UA/SSE, including regulations, norms, incentives (tax, subsidies, etc.), disincentives, specific projects coming from the public sector, etc.</p> <p>Describe any major policy changes or developments relevant for FWR/UA/SSE and how they came about.</p>	<p>Food waste is a municipal responsibility regulated at the local, regional, national and European level, by the following key norms. EU legislation requires that % of food waste is recycled by ...</p> <p>Food waste is included in the Barcelona food strategy 2030, with key lines of action including....</p> <p>Attempt in Barcelona to further separate food waste collection has faced social conflict and political battles between different parties, around cleanliness of the streets, etc.</p> <p>Another example is if a new regulation on food waste was implemented because of European legislation changes or because of societal pressure, or linked to climate targets, etc.</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented if needed by interview data.</p> <p>Focus should be on local regulations and plans, and from the analysis of those link to higher levels of administration.</p>
	<p>What are the main actors operating in the FWR/UA/SSE arena in the city? What type of activities do they conduct in relation to governance (policy-making participation, non-engagement with public sector, self-organisation, awareness raising, advocacy, etc.)?</p> <p><i>Max. 2000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe the diversity of the social movements/community organisations/civic FSIs that deal with FWR/UA/SSE , the type of activities they conduct in relation to governance and what is their approximate distribution between grassroots-led initiatives and more institutionalized projects (or hybrid models).</p> <p>Describe the diversity of private sector enterprises operating, the existing business models (platform-based enterprise, multinational corporation, localized company), ownership regimes (for-profit enterprise, social enterprise, cooperative), and the type of activities they conduct in relation to governance.</p> <p>Describe the different public sector institutions</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented if needed by interview data.</p> <p>Could include mapping outputs from WP2.</p>	

	<p>engaged locally and the type of activities they conduct in relation to governance.</p> <p>What is the <i>relationship between different actors</i>: public, private and civil society?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>What are their discourses, framings and aims around this topic? Do they converge or clash?</p> <p>How do they relate to each other? Do they engage in each other's initiatives?</p> <p>Are there spaces of coordination? Are there specific projects for collaboration?</p>		<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented if needed by interview data.</p> <p>Focus should be on interactions and relationships at the local level.</p>
<p>What are the main placed-based enablers for and barriers to sustainable food sharing in the city?</p>	<p>What are the main enablers to food sharing practices around FWR/UA/SSE in the city? Are they also relevant outside of the locality? How do they relate to global trends?</p> <p><i>Max. 2000 words</i></p>	<p>Identify enablers and if they are local or linked to processes outside</p> <p>Describe how these enablers affect different actors: public sector, private and civil society.</p> <p>Discuss if some of the identified enablers are dominated by a particular group of actors.</p> <p>Describe the evolution over time of the enablers to food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE.</p>	<p>Increased awareness of the climate impact of food waste internationally has led to the city council developing action to decrease their carbon footprint. Also local activist groups linked to international debates and movements such as Extinction Rebellion have fostered community actions on the topic...</p> <p>Food waste legislation changes at the regional level are fostering changes in food enterprises in relation to the generation of food waste, mostly by redistributing food to be wasted to avoid fines.</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p> <p>We will provide a tree code for enablers and challenges</p> <p>Focus should be on local aspects, and from the analysis of those link to higher levels of administration if relevant.</p>
	<p>What are the <i>main challenges</i> to food sharing practices around FWR/UA/SSE in the city? Are they also relevant outside of the locality? How do they relate to global trends?</p> <p><i>Max. 2000 words</i></p>	<p>Identify challenges and if they are local or linked to processes outside</p> <p>Describe how these challenges affect different actors: public sector, private and civil society.</p> <p>Discuss if some of the identified challenges are dominated by a particular group of actors.</p> <p>Describe the evolution over time of the challenges to food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE.</p>		<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p> <p>We will provide a tree code for enablers and challenges</p> <p>Focus should be on local aspects, and from the analysis of those link to higher levels of administration if relevant.</p>
	<p>Are there conflicting interests among different actors involved in FSIs related to</p>	<p>Discuss if some of the enablers that apply to a particular group of actors can simultaneously be challenges to another group of actors.</p>	<p>Strict regulations for food waste and redistribution, for instance, could be a barrier to community initiatives on this</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview</p>

	<p>FWR/UA/SSE?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe how these conflicts of interests have affected the relationships between groups of actors.</p> <p>Describe how these conflicting interactions and related power relations have evolved over time.</p>	<p>matter. However, this simultaneously leaves space for private companies to develop food waste businesses such as Too Good To Go or other existing apps.</p>	<p>data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p>
	<p>What is the influence of the previously analysed regulatory regime on these trends? How does the food sharing landscape affect potential enablers and challenges to FWR/UA/SSE?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe the relevance of the local food sharing governance landscape in the distribution of enablers and barriers to FWR/UA/SSE among different groups of actors.</p> <p>Discuss if the regulatory regime locks-in or counters the existing conflicts of interest and power relations around food sharing practices of FWR/UA/SSE.</p>		<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p> <p>Establish additional links if any to the analysis of existing regulations and plans as well as actors conducted for RQ1.</p>
<p>What is the influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context in shaping FSIs in the Hub locations?</p>	<p>Are there particular features of the cultural context of the city (understood as the diverse set of customs and knowledges of the different ethnic and national communities inhabiting the city) that are particularly relevant for food sharing practices around FWR/UA/SSE?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe the influence of the cultural context on the different groups of actors (public sector, private and civil society) in relation to food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE.</p> <p>Describe the evolution over time of the cultural context of the city, and how it has affected food sharing practices of FWR/UA/SSE.</p>	<p>Migratory trends have recently increased the diversity of the city, bringing food sharing practices that were not previously codified in local legislation. This has pushed the city council to adapt to the new cultural context by updating legislations and promoting new forms of urban food sharing.</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p>
	<p>What are the particular features of the socio-political context of the city that are particularly relevant for food sharing practices around FWR/UA/SSE?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>Describe the influence of the socio-political context on the different groups of actors (public sector, private and civil society) in relation to food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE.</p> <p>Describe the evolution over time of the socio-political context of the city, and how it has affected food sharing practices of FWR/UA/SSE .</p>	<p>Barcelona has a long tradition of anti-hegemonic struggles that give way to grassroots self-organisation. This has translated on a thriving cooperativist movement that hosts many food sharing initiatives and strongly shapes their governance</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p>
	<p>What are the particular features of the ecological and climatic</p>	<p>Describe the influence of the ecological and climatic context on the different groups of</p>	<p>Global heating has prompted a city to develop a network of climate shelters. Urban</p>	<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents</p>

	<p>context of the city that are particularly relevant for food sharing practices around FWR/UA/SSE?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>actors (public sector, private and civil society) in relation to food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE.</p> <p>Describe the evolution over time of the ecological and climatic context of the city, and how it has affected food sharing practices of FWR/UA/SSE.</p>	<p>gardens are among the green spaces that provide protection from extreme heat, and the council thus promotes their consolidation and development.</p>	<p>complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p>
	<p>What is the interaction of the previously described contextual characteristics relevant for food sharing around FWR/UA/SSE with higher levels of governance?</p> <p><i>Max. 1000 words</i></p>	<p>Discuss if the previously described relevant contextual features are specific to the city or if they apply to the region, the nation or even Europe as a whole.</p> <p>Discuss to what extent the food sharing governance landscape at different levels (regional, national and European) takes into account the contextual specificities around FWR/UA/SSE .</p>		<p>Document extraction and synthesis of documents complemented by interview data.</p> <p>Qualitative analysis using Atlas.ti</p>

2. Research design of the comparative study

The research will start with a desk-based analysis of key documents, followed by semi-structured interviews to key stakeholders. These interviews will provide new data and insights that might result in the inclusion of new secondary data in the analysis. The steps for the different analysis are detailed below.

2.1. Desk-based analysis

We will conduct an online search to retrieve key local documents tackling the three food sharing analysis. The online search will take place preferably on local repositories such as the ones from the local, regional and national administration. Members of the city administration partner of each local team can provide valuable knowledge to identify relevant repositories. Additionally, this can be complemented with google searches adding key local words. We will use a set of keywords for the online search. These will be translated to local languages of the different Hub locations with support of the European Food Sharing Dictionary created as part of the WP2 (T2.1). Local teams can also add extra keywords that they think could be relevant considering the local context.

List of keywords:

- food sharing
- urban garden
- urban agriculture
- community garden
- community composting
- community kitchen
- community cooking
- food waste
- food redistribution
- food surplus
- social and solidarity economy AND food

Documents will be selected when they respond to relevant governance categories such as:

- Local strategic plans and programmes
- Legislation: bills, ordinances, regulations, etc.
- Projects
- Official reports
- Existing studies on food sharing governance of the specific city

Each Hub location can complement this list with other types of documents that they might think relevant for conducting the analysis in their specific context.

Compilation of documents will be organised in a common spreadsheet, to be located on the CULTIVATE share point (WP4 > T4.1 Comparative Governance Analysis > Data). All local teams will contribute to the database, which will include links to access the referenced documents. The selection process will be revised and refined in the first weekly coordination meetings. In the local teams from the three Hub locations there are actors from local authorities or research institutions familiar with local landscapes which can contribute to ensure key documents are included. Once first results have been listed, discuss them with the Hub location team and conduct a second search taking into account the feedback provided. Repeat this process if needed.

Once the local Hub team is satisfied with the collected documents, we will process the database and conduct a qualitative content analysis. Further guidelines are included in table 2 and also in the report template and in the code tree shared by the UB team, in terms of type of information needed. Local teams will use the data analysis software Atlas.ti. The weekly coordination meetings will ensure that the analysis is consistent among the three Hub local teams.

2.2. Fieldwork for each case study

The data set will be defined using **purposive sampling methodology**, which will allow us to use a previously set criteria to hand-pick a reduced group of interviewees who are especially relevant for our investigation. Each Hub location will select between three and five participants for each of the food sharing arenas according to the following criteria:

- The sample must cover the three food sharing arenas, taking into account the priority research topics of each Hub location.
- Interviewees must have extensive experience in at least one of the food sharing arenas.
- The sample must include participants who have taken part in the governance of FSIs at a diversity of administrative levels and positionalities.
- The sample must include food sharing practitioners, government officials in relevant departments or agencies, and others if relevant.
- Most of the participants need to be based in the location of study and must be familiar with its local context.
- The sample must be gender diverse, and inclusion of minority populations when possible must be a priority.

Each city will recruit a group of minimum 10 key informants to be interviewed in depth. Information about the selection will be kept in the Database spreadsheet.

Each Hub location will then carry out semi-structured in-depth interviews of the previously selected participants. An initial template can be found on the CULTIVATE share point (WP4 > T4.1 Comparative Governance Analysis), that will evolve as we conduct the research. It will be discussed before the fieldwork phase starts and also the local team should adapt it to the specific context or person. Once completed, all interviews must be transcribed by each local team. The transcripts will be anonymised and titled in accordance with the reference assigned in the Database spreadsheet before being uploaded to the corresponding folder of the CULTIVATE share point. In line with the project compromise with open access knowledge production, interviews will eventually be uploaded to the CULTIVATE Zenodo repository, where they will be freely accessible. However, since they will be used for writing peer-reviewed articles, they will first be subject to an

embargo period that will last until the relevant articles have been published (see CULTIVATE Data Management Plan for more information).

Once the interview transcription process is finalised, each local team will process their transcriptions and conduct a qualitative content analysis addressed to complement the insights obtained through the desk-based analysis. As in the previous phase, we recommend using Atlas.ti, and weekly coordination meetings will be used to ensure cohesion among the analysis of the three Hub locations.

2.3. Outputs

Each local team will be in charge of producing a city report with the data obtained and analysed during the desk-based analysis and fieldwork. A detailed outline of the report can be found on the CULTIVATE share point (WP4 > T4.1 Comparative Governance Analysis), and corresponds with the structure of Table 2. We include below an overview of the structure:

1. Introduction:

- Importance of the different types of urban food sharing in the city
- Aims and goals of the report (provided by UB)
- Summary of content and findings
- Next steps:
 - Using the report to inform governance scenarios in the city and other ongoing processes in the city
 - Comparative analysis across cities to be conducted by UB.
 - Contribute with examples, insights to the menu of good food governance

2. Brief methodological note

- This section will be developed by UB, with specificities added by each local team

3. Urban food sharing governance landscape

3.1 UFS governance landscape analysis for food waste and redistribution

- Covering RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3

3.2 UFS governance landscape analysis for social and solidarity economy

- Covering RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3

3.3 UFS governance landscape analysis for urban agriculture

- Covering RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3

4. Conclusions

- Relevance of the findings

- Recommendations based on the analysis: to policymakers, practitioners, activists, etc.
- Potential future lines of research.

Once each local team has completed a first draft of their city report, the UB team will give detailed feedback. Each Hub location will then work on a final version of their city report. When the three city reports have been finalized, the UB team will use them to conduct the comparative governance analysis.

2.4. Timeline

Milestones:

- 25/08/23: written feedback on research protocol
- 08/09/23: completion of research protocol
- 22/12/23: complete drafts of city reports
- 17/01/24: written feedback on city reports
- 09/02/2024: final version of city reports
- 15/03/2024: comparative analysis completed

Figure 1: Timeline of the food governance landscape in Hub locations

3. Research limitations and ethical considerations

The main limitations of this research are geographical and temporal. The former refers to the limited number of cases and the fact they are all progressive Western-European cities of a similar size. This will be partially addressed in the next phase of the project, which will involve comparing the results with the realities of the seven Spoke locations, which prevents geographic biases and adds nuance to the conclusions and recommendations obtained in this research. The second limitation is temporal. The time to conduct the comparative analysis is limited, and therefore there are limits to the amount of data that we can collect. However, the fact that both researchers and participants are experts on urban food sharing governance ensures that the data obtained (both primary and secondary) is top quality and fully relevant for the analysis. Moreover, this analysis is connected to preliminary and subsequent project tasks that will complement the results over a longer time span.

The methodology chosen for this research makes the potential risks for both researchers and participants very low. As for physical risks, researchers might occasionally visit sites where different types of urban food sharing is practiced: urban gardens, kitchens, workshops, etc. However, they will play an observational role and they will be required to follow the health and safety regulations of the sites at all times. Interviews will be conducted in environments free of potential hazards. As for socio-political risks, we do not plan to involve vulnerable populations in our research and we do not expect to cover potentially sensitive topics in the interviews. Moreover, all research participants will be anonymised by default, unless they have fully understood the potential risks and wish their real names to appear. Participants will not receive economic compensation for their participation. However, since we expect them to be food sharing practitioners and advocates, they will be indirectly benefited by this research, which aims to contribute to developing progressive urban food sharing policies and local economies.

CULTIVATE members conducting the research must always share with interviewees the participant information sheet before interviews take place. This can be found on the CULTIVATE share point (WP4 > T4.1 Comparative Governance Analysis > Data). The participant information sheet contains basic information about the CULTIVATE project and about this specific analysis, as well as information related to GDPR. It is also the researchers' responsibility to ensure that participants read and understand the information contained in the sheet. When they have done so, they will need to fill and sign the informed consent form, which can be located on the CULTIVATE share point (WP4 > T4.1 Comparative Governance Analysis > Data). Only once these steps have been completed, will the researcher be able to start the interviewing process.

Interview transcripts will be anonymised and treated as shareable data. They will be uploaded to CULTIVATE's Zenodo repository and will be kept for five years after the end of the project. Data will be managed according to the Data Management Plan of the CULTIVATE project (Deliverable 1.2), completed in May 2023 and to be updated in December 2024.